

Publication

Design plan of the 3-level interventions

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Abstract

This document aims at sharing our design plans for our pedagogical interventions as part of the Work Package 3. It will outline the reasons for which we want to implement these actions and the scope, method, and means for each university intervention: instructional design (WP3A1), social participation in and outside university (WP3A2) and open recognition of skills (WP3A3).

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Project summary

This publication is a result of the Erasmus+ funded AGILE project (“Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition”, <http://www.agileproject-erasmus.eu/>), whose aim is to increase the resilience of HE systems to address the ongoing needs of refugees through social participation and skills recognition.

The AGILE project aims to enrich HE curricula by proposing new pedagogical designs that encourage grassroots and digitally enhanced actions in both formal and informal learning environments.

The project is coordinated by the University Paris 8. The consortium is made up of six universities (University Paris 8, Bordeaux Montaigne, University, University of Hamburg, University of Ljubljana, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Kaunas University of Technology), one think-tank (Polish Rectors Foundation) and one business partner (Web2Learn) specialised in open recognition systems and social learning.

Consortium

Partner n°	Name	Short name	Country	Logo
1.	University Paris 8	UP8	France	
2.	University Bordeaux Montaigne	UBM	France	
3.	Web2Learn	W2L	Greece	
4.	University of Ljubljana	UL	Slovenia	
5.	Polish Rectors Foundation	PRF	Poland	
6.	Lviv Polytechnic National University	LPNU	Ukraine	
7.	University of Hamburg	UH	Germany	
8.	Kaunas University of Technology	KTU	Lithuania	

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List of abbreviations

The following list presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution
MEnS	Migrants dans l'Enseignement Supérieur / Migrants in Higher Education
WP	Work Package

Introduction

While learning and mastering the host-country language remains the first prerequisite for exiled students wishing to return to education, it cannot in itself guarantee success in Higher Education (HE) or in society. As indicated in previous AGILE project reports, factors such as sustainable housing, grants, financial aid, professional, social and psychological help and access to specialized advisors to facilitate study are all key prerequisites for the successful integration of students in exile. Throughout the AGILE project, we have thus stressed the need for a support system that works alongside social partners, charities, associations and other local organizations which in turn encourages the constant improvement of language skills through regular exchanges with students and citizens.

This document aims at presenting the innovations in terms of pedagogy in France with the example of the French Bridge diploma (*DU Passerelle* in French). This innovation has led us to develop a 3-level intervention plan as part of the Work Package 3 (WP3) dedicated to all Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Europe and beyond which want to improve their pedagogical approach.

1. The French context

In France, the Syrian crisis in 2015 highlighted the need to build a coherent response and a model capable of adapting to large numbers of exiled students.

HEIs in France, unlike many of our AGILE partner HEIs, offer predominantly French-based degrees all of which are accredited by the HE ministry and all of which follow a given model and respect government criteria. Few bachelor degrees are taught solely in English and whilst more international masters do exist, they are often selective and very specific. So, for exiled students who wish to embark on post high school studies, a B2 or C1 level in French is a mandatory requirement. The fact that all degrees are national (because they are accredited every five years by the ministry) means that students can also change universities and integrate degrees if they have the necessary knowledge requirements. It is in this context that French HEIs began offering French language courses to exiled students.

French language courses are available in all French universities either through a French language center/faculty or a specific French language programme. These French language courses are, however, fee-paying (on average one semester of 16 hours a week costs 1000€). When universities welcome exiled students into their programmes, the cost is shouldered by the universities and sometimes additional funding is possible through projects with local authorities or Europe.

In France, in 2019, as demand increased and universities were faced with the complexity of welcoming refugee students, some universities got together and created the association MEnS¹ in order to implement a national framework securing government recognition of the

¹ The MEnS Network (Migrants in Higher Education) – This network is committed to developing and promoting a proactive policy for welcoming students and researchers in exile in French HEIs and the courses they offer.

diploma – The Bridge diploma (DU Passerelle)². This diploma seeks to give exiled students the level of French necessary to pursue their studies at a French HEI and ensures that every exiled student in France can access the same nationally recognized diploma. It also gives them a framework where they are entitled to grants and housing.

In the other AGILE partner countries, the context is a little different. More degree courses are taught in English but each country has its specificities.

2. The French Bridge diploma

It is an example of a language programme combined with a holistic support system that extends beyond the university campus, creating partnerships and bringing exiled students into direct contact with civil society. In France, knowledge of the national language is compulsory for university studies in HEIs, most of which are state-run. This Bridge diploma is a national diploma that enables refugee students to learn the national language (B2 for access to a Bachelor's degree and C1 for access to a Master's degree).

The national recognition of the diploma by the HE ministry has been an incredibly significant lever in improving the living conditions of refugee students because as a result, all students under 30 are eligible for student grants and university accommodation thus lifting two barriers to successful study and integration. The accreditation of these diplomas is renewed every 4 years so as to ensure continuous improvement and adaptation.

In general, roughly 70% of students enrolled in the Bridge programme obtain their diploma and continue their studies although not always in the field they had originally planned. Despite all the very positive aspects of this diploma, barriers remain and so new solutions and ideas have emerged over the years.

In 2023, 42 bridging diplomas were accredited and offered in 42 HEIs throughout France.

This diploma is the direct result of a collaboration between several stakeholders in the teaching of French as a foreign language in France. It can therefore serve as a “starting point” for partner countries welcoming refugees wishing to continue or start their university studies in these countries (see also Lawrance, 2024).

It is within this diploma that we will set up our 3-level intervention specific to the WP3 of the AGILE project.

The MEnS was behind the creation of the bridge diplomas. Today 56 HEIs are members of the MEnS network. <https://reseau-mens.org/>

² A national evaluation committee made up of specialists in French as a Foreign Language and experts in the welcoming of exiled students examines each application in relation to the framework model and the coherence of the hosting scheme. This committee assesses the proposed programme and the teaching methods used.

2.1. The Bridge Diploma – A holistic approach based on national guidelines

The French belief that a genuine transitional and holistic programme is essential, not only to master and consolidate fluency in the host language but also to prepare students for further studies, means that the bridge diploma does not merely give instructional guidelines but also gives allotted time for the development of social skills and ensures support and advice throughout.

The Bridge diploma is structured around the following points:

- French language acquisition classes with a view to academic, professional and social integration in France (levels A1 to B2/C1) which means approximately 200 hours of teaching per semester³;
- Intercultural and sports activities;
- Support for students in their administrative formalities, administrative procedures;
- Social, psychological and medical assistance;
- Help with orientation and returning to education.

It is also possible to offer complementary teaching methods such as tutoring, tandem programmes, observation courses and extra certifications (in languages, IT or other areas).

The aims of the diploma are thus language acquisition, facilitating a better understanding of the codes of the French HE system and facilitating integration into the university community through intercultural activities both in and beyond the campus.

2.2. Instructional design and pedagogical interventions in collaboration with associations providing training in skills and know-how

All French language classes include reception, production, mediation and interaction activities, both oral and written, according to the 6 CEFR levels of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR):

- beginners' levels: A1 / A2;
- intermediate levels: B1 / B2;
- advanced levels: C1 / C2.

³ For French language acquisition, one semester is necessary for each level. For a beginner in the French language, this means that 4 semesters are needed for the student to acquire a B2 level. Reaching the C1 level means that an exiled student will be more confident and struggle less in HE.

To determine students' level, a compulsory placement test is organized on arrival.

Each course must respect a range of teaching hours for each teaching unit:

Levels A: Hours per student

- Teaching unit 1: Oral comprehension 32.5 to 39 hours
- Teaching unit 2: Oral production including phonetics 52 to 58.5 hours
- Teaching unit 3: Written comprehension 19.5 to 26 hours
- Teaching unit 4: Written production including linguistic tools 78 to 84.5 hours
- Teaching unit 5: Intercultural and sports activities, associations and citizenship / Orientation and immersion for resuming studies / Integration into the university community 40 to 50 hours

Total = 222 to 258 hours per level (A1 and A2)

Levels B: Hours per student

- Teaching unit 1: Speaking activities 45.5 to 65 hours
- Teaching unit 2: Writing activities 65 to 78 hours
- Teaching unit 3: University Methodology 19.5 to 26 hours⁴
- Teaching unit 4: Complementary courses 26 to 52h (B1) 39 to 72h (B2)
- Teaching unit 5: Intercultural and sports activities, associations and citizenship / Orientation and immersion for resuming studies / Integration into the university community 40 to 50 hours

Total = 196 to 271h (B1) 202.5 to 278h (B2)

C1 level: hours per student

- Teaching unit 1: Oral Discourse Practice 45.5 to 58.5 hours
- Teaching unit 2: Written discourse 58.5 to 71.5 hours
- Teaching unit 3: Academic Methodology 19.5 to 26 hours
- Teaching unit 4: Complementary courses 39 to 72 hours
- Teaching unit 5: Intercultural and sports activities, associations and citizenship / Orientation and immersion for resuming studies / Integration into the university community 40 to 50 hours

Total = 202.5 to 278 hours

⁴ For students entering the second year of the bridge diploma (from B1 onwards), "French for academia" courses have been made compulsory. These courses are the first step towards a transition to HE and cover the following points: Understanding the French university system (types of courses, how knowledge is tested, who to contact in the event of difficulties, etc.); Understanding lectures and tutorials, and the work expected of students (training in note-taking, writing summaries, essays, oral presentations); Understanding exam and homework specifications, documentary research; Getting organised, preparing for exams...

Specific Features of Unit 5

Teaching unit 5 remains relatively open in the Bridge diploma curriculum and allows each HEI to decide on content according to its contacts with its wider environment, its human resources, etc. Effectively, as can be seen, cultural, social and intercultural activities, support for orientation and integration on campus and in the professional world are offered in this unit. A range of activities, tailored to students' language level, designed in partnership with local educational establishments and associations, are integrated into the diploma. These activities mean that each bridge diploma is anchored in its region and works with local organizations thus encouraging a sense of belonging and improving integration into the community.

Also, most bridge diplomas include learning support via tutors and language tandems. Individual support and monitoring for each student is a very important aspect and can range from tutoring⁵ to recruiting a designated member of staff to accompany students in the construction of their future study programme. Many bridge diplomas also include the opportunity to follow a full course in the desired diploma. This experience enables students to understand the work and investment needed to succeed and avoid the 'shock' of the first few weeks.

⁵ Bridge diploma students of all levels are able to benefit from tutoring (12 hours per semester) provided by students studying in the "French as a foreign language" master's course. As students reach the B1 level these sessions will be more closely linked to French for university purposes and will take the form of teaching projects, under the responsibility of the teachers from the French as a foreign language department.

2.3. A final word about organization

The preceding sections outline the key features of the national Bridge Diploma designed for students in exile who require proficiency in French to access HE in France. The establishment of a national framework ensures that all HEIs adhere to a standardized model, which includes structured French language instruction and implementation guidelines.

Although AGILE partner institutions such as Université Paris 8 (UP8) and Université Bordeaux Montaigne (UBM) both offer bridge diplomas, their operational approaches vary. Each institution has adapted the national model to align with its institutional context and specific capabilities:

- Inclusive French-language courses

Institutions such as Université Bordeaux Montaigne host language courses within their language center and offer complete academic programmes for international students, regardless of their mobility status. These programmes enable learners to attain proficiency levels ranging from A1 to C1, depending on the duration and objectives of their stay. UBM, for example, welcomes approximately 1,200 international students annually. In such contexts, exiled students enrolled in the Bridge Diploma are integrated into courses alongside other international learners. This inclusive approach fosters resilience and social integration by promoting intercultural interaction and reducing the risk of social isolation, as students engage with peers who do not share the same experiences of displacement or trauma.

- Dedicated language courses (only for exiled students)

Conversely, universities such as Université Paris 8 do not possess accredited French language centres. As a result, exiled students are enrolled in separate cohorts, which may inadvertently reinforce social isolation and hinder psychological recovery from experiences related to war and forced displacement. In these cases, it is imperative to actively facilitate opportunities for interaction with both international and French students. Such engagement is essential for effective integration and for fostering a deeper understanding of French language, culture, and society.

Both institutional models are widely represented within the French HE system. When implementing a Bridge Diploma, universities must consider these structural differences and tailor the programme accordingly. The inherent flexibility of the national model reinforces its potential as a scalable and adaptable solution for other national contexts seeking to establish inclusive, culturally responsive educational pathways for students in exile.

3. Design plan of a 3-level intervention

In light of the considerations outlined in the preceding sections and also drawing on student feedback from the Public Talk (see Lawrance, 2024, Section 2.3) as well as recent socio-linguistic studies addressing academic inclusion and linguistic appropriation among refugee populations ([2023 report produced by the Serafin Consortium](#)), it is proposed that the design and implementation of interventions 1) instructional design (WP3A3), 2) Social participation in and outside university (WP3A4) and 3) open recognition of skills (WP3A5), be guided by the following three core recommendations:

3.1. Revision of the curriculum of the Bridge diploma for courses exclusively reserved for exiled students

For those centres with dedicated language courses for exiled students, the curriculum needs to include spaces for more integrated activities. These activities should enable students to communicate beyond the classroom and campus, meeting French as well as international students as well as people from civil society. In this way, exiled students will no longer be in marginalised linguistic positions which only serve to reinforce, metaphorically, their 'exile'. Engagement with diverse academic and social environments is essential for inclusion both within and beyond HEIs.

This angle will be illustrated in our plan by the 1st level intervention: *instructional design* (WP3A3).

3.2. Social participation in and outside HEIs

In order to reinforce contacts and exchanges beyond the classroom, partnerships with artists, university libraries and associations will be put in place. The pedagogical activities developed will seek to promote principles that encourage active, participatory language acquisition. In this regard, the following pedagogical shifts are recommended:

- Transitioning from traditional foreign language learning to second language acquisition models that facilitate academic and social integration;
- Extending language learning beyond the classroom to include informal and extra-curricular contexts, moving from a purely instructional approach to one embedded in the broader university environment and community;
- Encouraging a shift from individualistic learning ('learning for oneself') to socially engaged practices ('giving of oneself'), fostering civic responsibility and community contribution.

This angle will be illustrated in our plan by the 2nd level intervention: *social participation in and outside university* (WP3A4).

As explained before, for the WP3A3, these new forms of inclusive language pedagogy can be implemented as part of the new curricula (Abdelkader et al., 2013; Aden, 2012; Dompmartin-Normand, 2023). The WP3A4 focuses on developing new activities inside and outside the university and organising artistic workshops and physical and digital exhibitions. Exploring a language through art can help exiled students express their experiences (and traumas) indirectly. It can also allow them to express themselves differently and activate the mechanism of resilience in a non-frontal way. Opening up a person's creativity helps to anchor language acquisition and vocabulary through experience.

3.3. Open recognition of skills (badges)

The proposed approach should reflect current developments in HE that emphasise openness and interdisciplinary learning. The integration of informal learning pathways – recognised through the issuing of Digital Credentials – should receive increased visibility so as to reward student engagement. The incorporation of these recommended measures into educational frameworks will also facilitate the development of essential soft skills throughout language acquisition journeys in the host countries.

The use of Open Badges will serve as formal recognition of key transferable skills such as autonomy, reflexivity, agency, metacognitive awareness and teamwork. These attributes are vital within both academic and broader socio-professional contexts, contributing meaningfully to lifelong learning trajectories (Zuhal Güven, 2020).

This new pedagogical approach extends beyond conventional formal learning and training environments. Within this framework, globality intersects with plurality, richness and transversality (Glissant, 1990/2010). This mode of learning is considered instrumental in enabling the transformation of traumatic experiences into resilience (Cyrulnik, 2005).

This angle will be illustrated by the 3rd level intervention: *open recognition of skills* (WP3A5).

These open badges will be attributed to refugee students, refugee graduate students and academic teachers that take part in at least one AGILE activity conducted under the WP3. Our aim is to issue 200 badges.

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Assistant lecturer in English. She was vice chancellor of Bordeaux Montaigne university from 2010 until 2020 and head of the French language department from 2017 until 2023. In these roles she was able to initiate the very first welcome programmes for exiled students and was responsible for coordinating their development and the regional projects which were vital in financing them. She has presented the different initiatives in place both at a local and international level and still works to improve curricula and student engagement through a variety of projects at the university.

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